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Review Article

REVIEW ON COSMECEUTICAL PREPARATIONPooja S. Gonge¹, Sushma G. Badhe², Mr. Sandeep C. Atram³^{1,2} Student Of Vidyabharati College of Pharmacy, C.k Naidu Camp, Amravati India³ Professor , Vidyabharati College of Pharmacy, C.k Naidu Camp, Amravati India**Article Received:** January 2023**Accepted:** January 2023**Published:** February 2023**Abstract:**

Cosmeceuticals means combination of cosmetics and pharmaceuticals. Cosmeceuticals are cosmetics products with biologically active ingredients purporting to have medical or drug-like benefits. Cosmeceuticals are used to improve and nourish the skin appearance and known to treat different dermatologic conditions, like cosmetics, cosmeceuticals are also applied topically having ingredients that influence the skin's biological function. Cosmeceuticals are meant to improve appearance by delivering nutrients necessary for healthy skin. cosmeceuticals usually claim to reduce wrinkles and to improve tone, texture and radiance of the skin. Cosmeceuticals products of herbal origin are most liked among clients as they are mostly non toxic and holding strong antioxidant activity. Cosmeceuticals products can be a drug, a cosmetics, or a combination of both. But the term 'cosmeceuticals' has no meaning under the law. Cosmeceuticals are not subject to be review by the Food and Drug Administration.

(FDA) and the term cosmeceuticals is not recognized by the federal food drug and cosmetics act. Although cosmetics and cosmetics and cosmeceuticals both are being tested for their safety and tested to determine weather beneficial ingredients actually live up to a manufacture's claim is not compulsory. The "cosmeceuticals" label applies only to products applied topically, such as creams, lotions and ointments, cosmetic labels do not have any divisions between active ingredients that are essential, they are all listed together. Sadick NS. Their role in dermatology practice. Cosmeceuticals represent a new category of products placed between cosmetics and pharmaceuticals that are intended for the enhancement of both the health and beauty of skin. Encompassing an ever-increasing part of the skin care industry, cosmeceuticals are formulated from a multitude of ingredients

Keywords : Cosmeceuticals, cosmeceutical chemistry, regulatory aspects, skin cosmeceutical, sunscreen agents, moisturizing agent, antiaging.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cosmetics are products that are used to cleanse and beautify the skin (Millikan, 2001). The first recorded use of cosmetics is attributed to Egyptians in 4000 B.C (Rona et al., 2004). Pharmaceuticals are essentially drug products and are defined as products that prevent, mitigate, treat or cure disease and /or affect the structure or function of the body (Vermeer and Gilchrest, 1996). Cosmeceuticals is a deliberate portmanteau of these two terms and is intended to connote drug like benefits from an otherwise cosmetic product. Kilgman may be described as the father of Cosmeceuticals, a term he popularized (Kilgman, 2005), but they first appeared in the world market in 1996 (Draelos, 1997). The scientific community has latched onto the flamboyant term. Between 1996 - 2007, over 837 articles have been published in reputable journals and over 600 have used the world cosmeceuticals as an authentic term (Mehta and Fitzpatrick, 2007). This may be the beginning of international recognition. Cosmeceuticals are generally presented as lotions or creams and are mostly targeted at dermatological issues (Choi and Berson, 2006).

Recently, orally delivered products of similar claims as cosmeceuticals have been defined as products that prevent, mitigate, treat or cure disease and /or affect the structure or function of the body (Vermeer and Gilchrest, 1996). Cosmeceuticals is a deliberate portmanteau of these two terms and is intended to connote drug like benefits from an otherwise cosmetic product. Kilgman may be described as the father of Cosmeceuticals, a term he popularized (Kilgman, 2005), but they first appeared in the world market in 1996 (Draelos, 1997). The purported drugs-like effects are largely unproven and the term is neither recognized by the United State's food and drug administration nor by any other regulatory body. The scientific community has latched onto the flamboyant term. Between 1996 - 2007, over 837 articles have been published in reputable journals and over 600 have used the world cosmeceuticals as an authentic term (Mehta and Fitzpatrick, 2007). This may be the beginning of international recognition. Cosmeceuticals are generally presented as lotions or creams and are mostly targeted at dermatological issues (Choi and Berson, 2006). Recently, orally delivered products of similar claims as cosmeceuticals have been labeled as either oral cosmeceuticals or as nutricosmetics or nutraceuticals. Commonly, all these are simply called cosmeceuticals. Recently an alarming term

called physician dispensed cosmeceuticals has been used in the United States (Mehta and Fitzpatrick, 2007).

History

The term was coined in 1984 by Dr. Albert Kingman of the University of Pennsylvania describing a hybrid category of products mid-way on the spectrum of 'cosmetics and pharmaceutical'. A cosmeceutical is consensually accepted to exert a 'pharmaceutical therapeutic benefit' but not necessarily a 'biological therapeutic benefit'.

The history of cosmetics comes from ancient Egypt and Rome where women and men used scented oils/ointments for hygienic purposes, to moisten their skin and cover up body odor (Draelos, 2000). Women would carry their makeup boxes (in special jars) and keep them under their chairs at events / parties, while men who also wore makeup, did not transport cosmetics kits (Chaudhari and Jain, 2009). The history of cosmetic and skin care products has been reviewed from archaeological excavations to the modern-day health and adornment practices with a current marketplace perspective (Chaudhari and Jain 2009; Draelos, 2000). Pertaining to sex differences in skin characteristics, men have a higher sebum (oil) content compared to women due to the influence of androgen hormones.

CLASSIFICATION OF COSMECEUTICAL

Cosmetics are broadly categorized into four types:

- Skin Cosmetics
- Hair Cosmetics
- Nail Cosmetics
- Cosmetics for hygiene purpose.

Skin Cosmetics

Skin care is a range of practices that support skin integrity, enhance its appearance, and relieve skin conditions. They can include nutrition, avoidance of excessive sun exposure, and appropriate use of emollients. Practices that enhance appearance include the use of Cosmetics, Botulinum, Exfoliation, fillers, Laser resurfacing, Microdermabrasion, peels, retinol therapy, (John Wiley and sons, 2010) and ultrasonic skin treatment. (Rudulfo, Kristina 2018) Skin care is a routine daily procedure in many settings, such as skin that is either too dry or too moist, and prevention of dermatitis and prevention of skin injuries. (Kottner J. 2015)

Skin care is a part of the treatment of wound healing, radiation therapy and some medications.

Classification of Skin Cosmetics:

1. Skin Cream

- Cleansing and Cold Cream.
- Foundation and Vanishing Cream
- Hand and Body Cream
- Night and Massage Creams

2. Powder

- Face powder
- Compact
- Body Powder

3. Skin Colourants

- Lipstick

4. Sunburn Product

- Sunscreen

It includes Cleansing, Toning, Cold Cream and Moisturizing

- Cleansing and Cold Cream -

Cold cream is mainly used for skin treatment such as facial mask or lip balm, due to its moisturising property. It can also be used to remove make up and as a shaving cream. cold cream gives the prolong contact type in the site of application as compare to the others semisolid dosage form or formulations. They give elegancy to the skin and it is not that much greasy. These type of creams are water-in-oil type of emulsions. Due to the oil phase, it gives an emollient to They produce cooling sensations by the evaporation of water, after their application on to the skin, hence known as cold creams. They should possess emollient action and the layer left on the skin after application should be non-occlusive. (De groot AC (1990) labelling cosmetics with their ingredients. Br Med J 30: 1636-1638)

1. Skin Cream

Creams are semisolid emulsions containing mixture of oil and water. There are consistency varies between liquids and solids.

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	Ponds cold cream	N. N. Impex, MT's Store, Tubecon India LLP
2.	Emami cold cream	Emami limited
3.	Dove (cleansing cream)	Unilever

- Foundation and vanishing cream -

Foundation is a liquid, cream or powder make up applied to the face and neck to create and even, uniform colour to the complexion, cover flaws and, sometimes, to change the natural skin tone. Some foundations also functions as a moisturizer, sunscreen, astringent or base layer for more complex cosmetics. Foundation applied to the body is generally referred to as "body painting" or "body make up" it is also known as vanishing cream which are apply to skin to provide a smooth emollient base before the application of face powder and other face make up. (Conway, Julia 2004)

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	Lakme	Hindustan Unilever
2.	Max factor	Stamford, Connecticut
3.	Ponds	safeFlex, HDPE Pond liner
4.	Charmis	BATTERIES, TELECOM

➤ Hand and Body cream -

A hand cream is a special formulation that is meant to nourish the skin on the hands and provide it with the protection it needs. a good hand cream will soothe your hands, leaving them soft and supple. It will also repair and undo the damage of neglect on your hands. Lotions and hand cream will provide relief. Rough areas like elbows and knees can hugely benefit from a little moisturizing hand lotions or cream. A perfect way to make skin free from rough and dry spots. Regularly applying a cream will soften hard skin and make it easier to reduce dry skin. (Chaudhari, SK; Jain, N.K., Asian J. Pharm. 2009)

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	NIVEA Body Lotion	Beiersdorf
2.	Ponds body cream	Unilever
3.	Oxyglow body cream	Oxyglow Cosmetics

➤ Night Cream –

Night cream is only to be applied in the evening, it has been formulated specially to make the most of the skin's 'nighttime rhythm', in which it regenerates and repairs the day's damage. A night cream can help to calm and soothe your skin overnight so that any redness or irritation is banished while you sleep. These help to ensure that, by morning, you have a clear skin complexion. If you have acne or breakouts, the temptation is to dry out your skin. Most night creams are enriched with vitamins A, C, E, anti-aging components, essential oils like rose oil, olive oil, jasmine oil, moisturizing ingredients like honey, shea butter, cocoa butter, amino acids, other antioxidants and collagen-forming particles. (Spencer, T. S. Clin. 1998)

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	Lotus Herbal Night Cream	Lotus Herbals Colour Cosmetics
2.	Khadi Natural Night Cream	Khadi Natural Healthcare
3.	Dot and Key Retentional Night Cream	RSH Global

2. Powder

The main property of face powder is to impart a smooth finish to the skin, masking of minor visible imperfections, masking of shine due to moisture or grease. Powders are considered as one of the important products of skin care preparation. They are widely used by both men and women. (D. Ida and L. Ana 2007)

➤ Face Powder –

Face powder is a cosmetic product applied to the face to serve different functions, typically to beautify the face. Originating from ancient Egypt, face powder has had different social uses across cultures and in modern times, it is typically used to set makeup, brighten the skin and contour the face. Powder atop liquid or cream foundation helps to set it so that it won't migrate into any lines or slide down on your face. Certain powders can also reduce the look of fine lines and pores. Powder is also a great base upon which to apply blush, contour, bronzer, or shimmer. Face powders provide coverage of complexion imperfections, oil control, a matte finish, and tactile smoothness to the skin. Powders give a good lasting effective foundation makeup and possess oil-absorbing properties that are useful for oily skin types. (D. Giovanni, V. Arcoraci, and L. Gambardella 2006)

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	White Tone	Vini Cosmetics Private limited
2.	Yardely London	Wipro (Indian multinational conglomerate)
3.	Ponds powder	Ponds India Ltd
4.	Spinza Talc Powder	Cavinka Private Limited

➤ Compact powder –

Compact powder is one of the most used commonly used makeup products, it is lightweight powder that usually comes in a powder form. It is used to give your face a light coverage or to give your makeup the perfect finish. There are a lot of women who skip using a compact powder while doing their makeup. It is pressed into a pan and can be used to get rid of the excess oil and sweat on your face. A compact powder also adds light coverage to your skin and even out your complexion. On days when you want to opt for light makeup, you can just use some concealer and compact powder to do your base makeup (Z. Draelos, and J DiNardo,2006)

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	Faces Canada Compact powder	Regi India Cosmetics Pvt. Ltd.
2.	Lackme Flawless Compact Powder	Hindustan Unilever
3.	Maybilline New York Fit Me Compact Powder	L'oreal company

➤ Body Powder –

Body powder (is also known as dusting powder) is a deodorant in powder form that absorbs sweat and masks body odour . There are body (dusting / talcum powders) face powders and compacts medicated powders form that absorbs sweat and masks body odour. Face powders generally come in two main types. One of which is loose powders, which is used to assist with oily skin in absorbing excess moisture and mattifying the face to reduce shininess. The other is pressed powder which conceals blemishes and maximises coverage. Tap a quarter-sized amount of dusting powders into the palm of your hand or sprinle directly onto your body. Pat evenly over skin to stay fresh, dry and silky smooth. Add more if needed. Gently rub dusting powder onto areas that tend to get a bit sweaty as it will keep skin dry and smooth.(R. Wolf, and L. Parish,1994)

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	NIVEA Talcum Powder	Akhil Enterprises
2.	De Belle Fairness Talc	AGS Incorporation

3.Skin Colourants

Colourants are soluble (In water or in oil) synthetic organic colouring agents. They are used to colour cosmetics products such as skin care or toiletries, among others, Meanwhile, pigments are insoluble colouring agents, which when used, remain in the form of crystals or particles. Red, yellow, orange, blue and a no. of other shades can be develop using organic pigments. Annatto seed powder, caramel red carmine, pink carmine, purple carmine and beta carotene are widely used as a colorants in cosmetics. (A. Weisz, A. L. Scher 2007)

➤ Lipstick

Lipstick is a waxy solid usually coloured cosmetic in stick form for the lips. also : a stick of such cosmetic with its case. Most lipsticks are made from three basic ingredients: wax, oil, and pigment. Pigment is the colour . Waxes provide shape and a spreadable texture. Oils such as petrolatum, lanolin, cocoa butter, jojoba, castor, and mineral and moisture.(B. Valet, J.Ginestar, 2007)

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	Maybelline	L'Oréal Group
2.	Lakme	Tata Oil Mills Company (TOMCO)
3.	Elle 18	Hindustan Unilever Young and vibrant

4.Sunburn products

Sunburn products are defined as substances that protect the skin from the harmful effects of solar UV radiation by absorbing, reflecting, scattering, or otherwise deflecting UV photons, avoiding their absorption by the components of the skin. Sunburn treatment doesn't heal your skin, but it can ease pain, swelling and discomfort. If care at home

doesn't help or your sunburn is very severe, your health care provider might suggest a prescription corticosteroid cream.

➤ Sunscreen

They are considered as one of the important preparation of cosmetics. They provide protection against sunburn. They also help in absorbing the portion of erythema on the skin caused by sun's radiant energy. In winter high proportion of UV rays are reflected than summer. Sunscreens are ingredients that intend to prevent the harmful U.V radiations in sunlight from penetrating the skin layers both physically and chemically. Added to cosmetic formulations, they protect the skin from sunburns and other damages caused by harmful UV radiations.(Robinson, J.K.; Rigel,D.S.;Amonette,R.A..J.Am.Acad.2000)

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	Mamaearth hydragel Indian sunscreen SPF 50	Hitech Formulations Pvt. Ltd.,
2.	Wow body sunscreen	Kapco International Ltd.

Hair care cosmetics

Hair Cosmetics are an important tool that helps to increase patient's adhesion to alopecia and scalp treatments. Hair cosmetics includes Shampoo, Conditioners, hair straightening products, hair dyes and henna; The dermatologists knowledge of hair care products, their use, and their possible side effects can extend to an understanding of cosmetic resources and help dermatologists to better treat hair and scalp conditions according to the diversity of hair types and ethnicity. (Kamath YK, Weigmann HD; Madnani N, Khan k. Hair cosmetics. Indian J Dermatol Venereol Leprol.2013)

❖ Shampoo

A shampoo is a preparation of surfactant (i.e. surface active material) in a suitable form-Liquid, Solid or Powder-which when used under the specified conditions will remove surface grease, dirt, and skin debris from the hair shaft and scalp without adversely affecting the user.

Shampoos are not only scalp cleaners, but indubitably act as preventing the hair shaft damage. Many scalp diseases are also treated by active ingredients that are added to the shampoo's formulations. It is desirable that whatever may the disease or condition be (dermatitis, seborrhea, alopecia, psoriasis), the hair strands are kept aesthetically presentable, preserving its softness, combability and shine while treating the scalp.(Shapiro J, Maddin S; Deeksha, Malviya R, Sharma PK; Trueb RM)

Shampoos are typically composed of 10–30 ingredients although products with as few as four ingredients are available. The products are grouped

into: (1) Cleansing agents; (2) additives that contribute to the stability and comfort of the product; (3) conditioning agents, intended to impart softness and gloss, to reduce flyaway and to enhance disentangling facility, and (4) special care ingredients, designated to treat specific problems, such as dandruff and greasy hair.(Deeksha, Malviya R, Sharma PK.2014; Draelos ZD, 2005)

Conditions that are mostly affected by the use of aggressive shampoos are: Difficulty in untangling the strands, and the frizz effect. Attrition, the main cause of frizz, can be minimized by adequate formulation of cleaning products. On the other hand, if the shampoo formulas do not present the adequate composition, fiber attrition is aggravated.(Shapiro J. Maddin S. Medicated shampoo,1996; Draelos ZD, 2005)

Although considered as safe products, shampoos can cause contact dermatitis. Common allergens in shampoos are: Cocamidopropyl betaine, methylchloroisothiazolinone, formaldehyde-releasing preservatives, propylene glycol, Vitamin E (tocopherol), parabens and benzophenones. (Trueb RM. Shampoos: Composition and clinical applications. Hautaezt.1998)

Types of Shampoo -

Shampoos are of the following types:

- Powder Shampoo
- Liquid Shampoo
- Specialized Shampoo
 - Conditioning Shampoo
 - Anti – dandruff
 - Baby shampoo
- Powder shampoo-

Powder shampoo is the same as liquid shampoo, just in powder form. Powder dry shampoo is a product that absorbs excess oil and eliminates dirt from your hair without the need for water. It contains corn starch powder to eliminate greasiness and leave your hair fresh. Powder dry shampoo is a product that

absorbs excess oil and eliminates dirt from your hair without the need for water. It contains corn starch powder to eliminate greasiness and leave your hair fresh. (Deeksha, Malviya R, Sharma PK.2014; Draelos ZD, 2005)

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	MahaGrow	MahaGro Hortitech Industries Pvt. Ltd.
2.	Ktein	Omorose

➤ Liquid shampoo-

Shampoo is a hair care product, typically in the form of a viscous liquid, that is used for cleaning hair. Less commonly, shampoo is available in solid bar format. Shampoo is used by applying it to wet hair, massaging the product into the scalp, and then rinsing it out. Shampoo is typically in the form of a viscous liquid with some exception of waterless solid form such as a bar. Shampoo was developed to replace soap for cleansing scalp and hair by removing unwanted sebum, dandruff, environmental dust, and residues of hair care products. (Shapiro J. Maddin S. Medicated shampoo,1996; Draelos ZD, 2005)

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	linic plus shampoo	Hindustan Unilever
2.	Sunsilk shampoo	Unilever
3.	Tresemme shampoo	Unilever

➤ Specialized Shampoo – it includes following types of shampoo

Conditioning shampoo – Conditioning shampoos are formulated to provide the dual benefit of a shampoo as well as conditioner. It is a sophisticated hair care product, which has a shampoo and conditioner in one. In other words, a single product can be rather than using separate shampoo and conditioner. after shampoo cleans and removes oils, conditioner reintroduces moisture back into your hair and helps to smooth your strands for a shiny, soft, healthy finish. It is kind of like how you wash your face and then apply moisturizer. (Trueb RM. Shampoo Composition and clinical applications. Hautaezt.1998)

thymol and camphor as anti-dandruff agent. There are three types of conditioning shampoo-

1. rinse-out conditioners. These are the most common type of conditioners for all hair types.
2. Deep Conditioners. Deep Conditioners or hair masks are treatments that will help hydrate, repair or nourish you hair.
3. Leave-in Conditioners.

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	L'Oreal Professional Serie Expert Vitamino Color Shampoo	L'OREAL India Pvt. Ltd.
2.	Vaadi Herbals Superbly Smoothing Heena Shampoo	Vaadi Herbals Pvt. Ltd.

Anti-dandruff shampoo – Anti- Dandruff shampoo is a specialty shampoo that contains antifungal and antimicrobial ingredients like ciclopirox and zinc pyrithione to help relieve itching and flaking, build up, and excess sebum production in your scalp. It reduces itching, flaking, irritation, and redness of the scalp. Selenium sulfide is also used for a condition that causes discoloration of the skin (tinea versicolor). This medication belongs to a class of medications called anti-infectives. It works by slowing the growth of the yeast that causes the infection.

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	Nizoral A-D - Belgian pharmaceutical company	Belgian pharmaceutical company
2.	Jason Dandruff Relief	hain celestial group, inc.

Baby shampoo Baby shampoo is a hair care product that is used for the removal of oils, dirt, skin particles, dandruff, environmental pollutants and other contaminant particles that gradually build up in hair; specially formulated for use on infants and young children by means of substituting chemicals. Baby shampoos use milder surfactants (known as amphoteric surfactants) that clean without causing eye irritation that's why baby shampoos are labelled "tear-free." Another characteristic of amphoteric surfactants is that they don't foam as well as sulfates and they're not as good at removing oil and product buildup.

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	Himalaya Herbals Gentle Baby Shampoo	The Himalaya Drug Company
2.	Sebamed Childrens Shampoo	Sebapharma GmbH & Co. KG
3.	Mee Mee Mild Baby Shampoo	Me N Moms Pvt. Ltd.

Nail Cosmetics

Nail are transparent protective covering on finger, tips and toes of feet. The care of nails is referred to as Manicuring. Nail beautification is a big industry today, with various nail cosmetics available, ranging from nail hardeners, polishes, extensions, artificial/sculpted nails, and nail-grooming procedure or as a reaction to the individual components of the nail cosmetics.

A set of manicure preparations consist of a no. of different cosmetic product which are concerned with cleansing and decoration of nails. (Jain SK Sharma NK. Textbook pf pharmaceuticals. Vallabh Prakashan; 2005)

➤ Nail Polish

Nail Polish is lacquer that can be applied to the human finger nail or toenails to decorate and protect the nail plates. Nail polish (also known as nail varnish or nail enamel) is a lacquer that can be applied to the human fingernail or toenails to decorate and protect the nail plates. The formula has been revised repeatedly to enhance its decorative properties and to suppress cracking or peeling. Nail polish consists of a mix of an organic polymer and several other components that give it colours and textures. Nail polishes come in all colour shades and play a significant part in manicures and pedicures. (Elsner, maibach-cosmeceutical drugs vs. cosmetics.)

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	Colorbar Nail Polish Colorbar Cosmetics Pvt. Ltd	Colorbar Cosmetics Pvt. Ltd.
2.	Lakme Nail Polish	Hindustan Unilever.
3.	Elle 18 Nail Polish	RK World Infocom Pvt Ltd

➤ Thinner

thinner (plural thinners) A liquid substance used to thin the consistency of another liquid. Turpentine or mineral spirits can be used as a thinner for oil-based paints. Something that thins. Pomegranate juice and exercise are great natural blood thinners. A thinner is a volatile solvent that is used to dilute or extend oil-based paints or cleanup after use. Common solvents used as paint thinner chemicals include mineral spirits, mineral and true turpentine, acetone, naphtha, toluene, methyl ethyl ketone (MEK), dimethylformamide (DMF), glycol ethers and xylene. (Thiele JJ, Ekanayake Mudiyansele S, Hsieh SN. Cosmeceuticals vitamins: vitamin E.)

Sr. no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	OPI Nail Lacquer Thinner	OPI PRODUCTS, INC.

Cosmetics for hygiene purpose

Hygiene products means goods, merchandise or products necessary for the personal health, safety and cleanliness of an individual. (J Soc Cosmet Chem 1990) Personal hygiene products are products that have been manufactured in the cosmetics industry, but do not carry the legal classification of cosmetics, which we use to clean ourselves in our daily

lives. They are intended for use on the skin, hair, or teeth. Despite the fact that everyone is familiar with many of them. There are certain products which are used for hygiene purpose (Sainio E-L, Kanerva L 1995)

Desodorants

special substance to combat the bad odours that our armpits emit due to perspiration. If it does not come in spray form, it should not be shared under any circumstances.

Brush and toothpaste: these are the utensil and paste that we use to brush our teeth. It is basic common sense not to share it.

Soaps

this is a sodium or potassium salt resulting from a specific chemical reaction, saponification (mixture of an alkali and a lipid). It can be found in a bar, powder, cream or liquid form.

Sr no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	Godrej no.1	Godrej Consumer Products Limited (GCPL)
2.	Himalaya	Himalaya Global Holdings Ltd.

Shampoos

These are specific soaps used to clean our hair.

Sr no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	Clinic plus shampoo	Hindustan Unilever
2.	Sunsilk shampoo	Unilever

Colognes and lacquers

these are substances obtained through chemical processes and reactions that allow us to smell better and fix our hair in place.

Brush and toothpaste

These are the utensil and paste that we use to brush our teeth. It is basic common sense not to share it. (Sainio E-L, Kanerva L 1995)

r no.	Name	Manufacturer
1.	Pepsodent - Unilever	Unilever
2.	Colgate	Colgate-Palmolive Company
3.	Meswak	Balsara Hygiene

LIST OF COSMECEUTICAL INGREDIENTS

Sl.	Ingredient	Purported action	Sources	Marketed Preparation
1	Allatonin	Skin Smoothing	Comfrey (Fm. Boraginaceae)	Soft cleansing emulsion
2	Aloe vera	Softens skin	aloe vera (Fm. Asphodebceae)	Lotus herbal moisturizers
3	Alpha. hydroxy acids(AHA)	Exfoliates and improves circulation	Fruit acids (glycolic acid, lactic acid, citric acid, tartaric acid, pyruvic acid, maleic acid, etc.	Garnier anti wrinkle preparation
4	Arnica	Astringent & soothing	Arnica montana (Fm. Asteraceae)	Arnica herbal cream
5	Arjunolic extract	Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory	Terminalia arjuna (Fm. Combretaceae)	Himalaya Arjuna
6	Beta hydroxyl acids(BHA)	Antibacterial	Salicylic acid (Salix alba)	Oxy-med shampoo
7	Beta-Carotene	Minimizes lipid peroxidation and cellular antioxidant	Carrots and tomatoes (Fm. Umbelliferae, Solanaceae)	Environ body cream
8	Boswellia	Anti-inflammatory and anti aging	Boswellia serrata (Fm. Burseraceae)	Aroma silk boswellia anti-wrinkle cream
9	Calendula.	Soothes, softens skin, and promotes cell formation.	Calendula officinalis (Fm Asteraceae)	Weleda calendula paste

10	Centella	Skin conditioning agent increases collagen production, improves texture and integrity of skin, and reduces Appearance of stretch marks.	Centella asiatica (Fm. Mackinlayaceae)	Keratin complex
11	Coleus forskolii oil	Antimicrobial aromatherapy/perfumer	Coleus sps.	Ayush neem plus
12	Coriander seed oil	Anti-inflammatory and anti-irritant, skin. lightening properties	Coriandrum sativa (Fm.Umbelliferae)	Tcc collagen complex
13	Cucumber Cools res	Refreshes, and tightens pores	Cucumis sativus (Fm Cucurbiceae)	Eminence eye makeup remover
14	Dry extract from yarrow	Treatment of oily hair.	Achillea millefolium (Fm. Asteraceae)	Juniper yarrow moisturizer
15	Essential fatty acids	Smoothens, moisturizes and protects	Linolenic acids and arachidonic acid	Parachute hair oil
16	Furfuryladen ine	Improves hydration and texture of skin	Plant growth hormone	kinerase lips treatment
17	Lupeol	Antioxidant and skin conditioning treatment	Cractacva nurvula (Fm.capparidaceae)	Sea tonic stretch mark removing cream
18	Ginkgo	Antioxidant that smoothes rejuvenates and promotes youthful appearance	Ginkgo bloba (Fm.Ginkgoaceae)	Embryo revitalizer cream
19	Green tea extract	Antioxidant	green teas (Camellia sinensis)	Alchemy conditioner
20	Horse chestnut extract	Supports blood circulation wound healing effect and anti inflammatory	Aesculus hippocastanum (Fm.Hippocastanacea)	Sisley flower gel
21	Ivy	Stimulates circulation and helps other ingredients penetrate skin.	Hedera spp. (ivy family)	Pattern body wash
22	kinetin	Free radical scavenger and antioxidant	Plants and yeast	kinerase pro therapy
23	Licorice extract	Skin whitening properties, antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti inflammatory.	Glycyrrhiza glabra (Fm.fabaceae)	Liqourice balm
24	Neem oil	Antimicrobial	Azadirachta indica	Himalaya neem face wash

	limonoids		(Fm.Meliaceae)	
25	Oleanolic extract	Antioxidant, antifungal, improves texture and integrity of skin	Olive leaf	Trioxil an acne cream
26	Panthenol	Builds moisture and soothes irritation	Provitamin B5(broccoli, calf's liver turnip greens)	Penaten baby cream
27	Pycnogenol	Anti-aging effect	Grape seed extract	Isotonix
28	Retinoic acid	Smooths skin, promotes cell renewal and improves circulation to skin	Vitamin A (green leafy vegetables)	Renova cream
29	Sodium hyaluronate	Lubricant between skin tissues and maintains natural moisture	Natural protein	Pevonia botanica
30	Rosemary extract	Antioxidant antimicrobial and Anti inflammatory	Rosemarinus officinalis	L'Oreal body conditioner
31	Tetrahydrocurcuminoids	antioxidant and anti aging	curcuma longa (Fm. zingiberaceae)	Life extension super curcumin
32	Turmeric oil	Antibacterial and anti-inflammatory	curcuma longa (Fm.zingiberaceae)	Vicco turmeric cream
33	Ursolic acid	Anti-inflammatory, collagen buildup	Rosemanus officinalis (Fm.Lamiaceae)	Holy basil extract
34	Vitamin A	Anti-oxidant	Vitamin A,C,E (lemon, citrus fruits, oil from sunflower and safflower)	Everyuth peel
35	Witch hazel	Tones	Hamamelis virginiana (Fm Hamamelidaceae)	Thayers skin toner

CURRENT COSMECEUTICALS COMPOUNDS AVAILABLE

➤ **Bo-Peptide Eye Cream**

HCG diet friendly mixture of various peptides and glycosaminoglycans along with the Lipo Light light reflecting technology.

➤ **Anti-Aging Eye Cream**

Powerful mixture of the anti-oxidants melatonin and Idebenone in Glycine Soya Protein solution, designed to restore youthful texture to skin. (Kuno N and Matsumoto M. 2004)

➤ **Bacopeptide Anti-Aging**

HCG diet friendly formulation of Bacopa Monnieri extract, acetyl dipeptide and gluconol-actone in vanishing cream. (Ronaet al., 2004).

➤ **Collagen Booster Lotion**

HCG diet friendly formula to improve and restore skin matrix contains Palmitoylpentapeptide, glycine soya protein, kinetin and glycos aminoglycans. (Draelos ZD,2008.)

➤ **Eye Wrinkle Gel**

HCG diet friendly formula designed to provide maximum moisture to support skin matrix contains Sodium Hyaluronate, DMAE, Acetyl D (Glucosamine Ravichandran G, Bharadwaj VS, Kolhapur SA,2005.)

FUTURE TRENDS

NEED FOR STUDY ON COSMECEUTIALS -

Now a day it's not just the interest of people but certainly has become the need of the people to maintain a youthful & healthy appearance. Ultimately as the population in the world of the median age increases there is rise in the demand of the cosmeceuticals. Over 560 million people in India are in the age group of 18-35 years. As median age increases, the market is going to boom, especially growing number of women in the workforce feeling the hassle to maintain a youthful and vibrant appearance. This resulted into a rapid growth of cosmeceuticals in the natural personal care industry. (Dooley, T. P. 1997).

As there is constantly growth in global market a lot of money is playing in hands of people at the same there is increase in the population with higher qualification and knowledge thus this class of population has become more beauty-conscious and thus is spending a

high amount of their earning in maintaining a youthful appearance i.e. in cosmeceuticals. Thus cosmeceuticals market has become one of the fastest growing markets throughout the globe. (Middleton, J.1974)

Development in technology and invention of new ingredients has further contributed to the progress in the commercialization of cosmeceuticals products world-wide. The market that reached to the mark of US\$ 27.2 Billion in 2010 is likely to augment at a rapid pace in the coming years with anti-aging skin care taking the top spot in revenue patterns. (Carraro, C. and M. A. Pathak.1988).

The cosmeceuticals demand in US is estimated to grow by 7.4% per year to \$8.2 Billion in 2012. The skin care segment will account for 63% of all cosmeceuticals product demand through 2012 and is expected to grow to \$22.1Billion in worldwide sales by 2013. (Stalling, A. F. and M.P.Lupo.2009).

Cosmeceuticals emphasize the functional aspects of cosmetic products. The cosmeceutical market, particularly its natural segment, with its promise to deliver effective cosmetics safely, will continue to expand. However, there are still some issues that have to be considered with in the industry. First and foremost, claims of efficacy have to be backed up. (Kang, W. H. S. C. Chun and S. Lee. 1998).

Proof of efficacy is becoming important now more than ever. Even though most cosmeceutical ingredients have scientific merits; questions still arise whether or not their concentrations in cosmetic formulations render them effective. Nowadays, consumers are very savvy and discriminative. With the wide variety of choices available, consumers will discontinue use of ineffective products. Consumers are also more natural consciousness. They are demanding the use of more and more natural ingredients as they have been more exposed to the negative press about chemicals and toxic substances. This has prompted the cosmetic companies to increase the uses of natural ingredients in their products, even if only for press purposes. Thus, natural products and extracts will continue to replace chemical ingredients as much as possible. In addition, animal sources will continue to be replaced by plant and Cosmeceuticals and Natural Cosmetics. (Welhourne, t.c.1995.)

CONCLUSION:

Cosmeceuticals offer both challenges and rewards to patients and their physicians. As society holds a

youthful and healthy appearance to be of utmost importance, many people feel anxious about their aging skin and seek physician advice on what to do. Helping patients understand the degree of improvement that can realistically be achieved as well as potential side effects remains the primary responsibility of the physician with regard to these products. Many of the new cosmeceuticals in development sound very exciting, but the physician's concern is to help patients choose the best products available today.

Some experts recommend that physicians pick one or two products with which they have experienced good results and advise their patients on how to incorporate them into their daily skin regimen--always reminding patients that even a safe product can evoke redness, cause irritation, or clog pores if used inappropriately.

As technology advances and cosmeceuticals continue to become more sophisticated and more widely used, the medical profession must continue to take an active role in familiarizing themselves with these products and in educating patients about the benefits and risks of cosmeceuticals.

REFERENCES:

- Pitanguy I. Future directions in plastic surgery. 3rd European congress in aesthetic dermatology and surgery & European congress of anti-aging medicine; 2007 Oct 12-14; Paris, France
- Seidenari S. Diagnostica non invasiva in dermatologia. Torino: EDRA S.r.l.; 1998.
- Zuang V. The use of non-invasive techniques on human volunteers to determine the safety and efficacy of cosmetic products (doctoral thesis). Nottingham: University of Nottingham; 1999.
- Serup J, Jemec GBE. Handbook of non-invasive methods and the skin. London: CRC Press; 1995.
- See Special Report: Skin Care's Changing Face, Business Week Online, <http://images.businessweek.com/db/04/11/cosmeceutical/cosmeceutic>.
- Millikan,(2001), Ronaetal.,(2004), Vermeer ans Glichrest,(1996), Kilgman,(2005), Draelos,(1997), Mehta and Fitzpatrick,(2007), Chio and Berson,(2006).
- Vermeer BJ, Gilchrest BA (1996). Cosmeceuticals. A proposal for rational definition, evaluation and regulation. Arch Dermatol. 132(3): 337-340.
- Zhou Chen, Jin Young Seo, Yeon Kyung Kim, Se Rah Lee, Kyu Han Kim, Kwang Hyun Cho, Hee Chul Eun and Jin Ho Chung, Heat Modulation of Tropoelastin, Fibrillin-1 and MatrixMetalloproteinase-12 in Human Skin In Vivo J Invest Dermatol, 2005; 124: 70-78.
- Muhammed majeed and Laxmi prakash, Sabinsacorporation, USA-Cosmeceuticals: A Revolution in the Making.
- Cosmeceutical Trends and Technologies: A Review of Global Technology Trends, Market Information, and Business Opportunities. Edition third.
- <http://newhope360.com/cosmeceuticals-taking-root-europe>.
- Dureja H. Kaushik D, Gupta M, Kumar V, Lather V. Cosmeceuticals: An emerging concept Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, University, Rohtak, India, 2004; 12: 12.
- Draelos ZD. The cosmeceutical realm. ClinDermatol. Nov-Dec 2008; 26(6): 627-32. [Medline].
- Elsner, maibach-cosmeceutical drugs vs. cosmetics.
- Sadick NS. Their role in dermatology practice (focus On: Cosmeceuticals). Journal of Drugs in Dermatology 2003. Available from: http://www.accessmLibrary.com/coms2/summary-0286-286-235_196_ITM. [Last accessed on 2007 Dec 10].
- Rona C, Vailati F, Berardesca E (2004). The cosmetic treatment of wrinkles. J. Cosmet.Dermatol. 3(1): 26-34.
- Padma PJ, Karthika K. Cosmeceuticals-an evolution; Int. J. Chem Tech Res.2009; 1(4).
- Kilgman AM (2005). Cosmeceuticals: A broad-spectrum category between cosmetics and drugs. In: Elsner P, Maibach H, eds. Cosmeceuticals and Active Cosmetics. Drug versus Cosmetics, Boca Raton, Fla: Tylor and Francis pp. 1-9.
- Draelos ZD (1997). New developments in cosmetics and skin care products. Adv.Dermatol. 12: 3-17.
- <http://newhope360.com/cosmeceuticals-taking-root-europe>.
- <http://www.wisegeek.com/what-is-cosmetics-history.htm>.
- Cosmeceuticals to 2012-Market Research, Market Share, Market Size, Sales, Demand Forecast, Market Leaders, Company Profiles, Industry Trends. Available from: <http://www.freedoniagroup.com/Cosmeceuticals.html> [Accessed on: June 24,2011].
- Klingman AM. Cosmetics a dermatologist looks to future: promises and problems.DermatolClin 2000; 18: 699-709.

24. Klingman A. the future of cosmeceuticals: an interview with Alberl Kligman, Interviewby zoe Diana Draelos *Dermatol Surg* 2005; 31 (7 pt 2): 890-1.
25. <http://www.insidecosmeceuticals.com/articles/2007/06/fulfilling-consumer-needs-in-the-changing-cosmeceu.aspx>.
26. Kuno N and Mastumoto M. (2004),
27. Puvabanditsin P, Vongtongsri R. Efficacy of Aloe vera cream in prevention and treatment of sunburn and suntan. *J. Med. Assoc. Thai.*, 2005; 88(4): S173-176.
28. Farrukh A, Mohammad AZ, Nagma K, Mark D, Hasan M. Protective effect of pomegranate derived Products on UVB-mediated Damage in human reconstituted skin. *Experimental Dermatol.* 2009; 18(6): 553-561.
29. Kaplan DL, Moloney SJ, Pinnel SR. A new stabilized ascorbic acid solution: Percutaneous absorption and effect on relative collagen synthesis. *J. cutaneous aging & cosmetic dermatol.* 1988; 1(2): 115-121.
30. Dover JS, *Cosmeceuticals: A Practical Approach*, Skin Care Physicians, Chestnut Hill, MA, USA Yale University School of Medicine, New Haven, CT, USA Dartmouth Medical School, Hanover, NH, USA. Vol 6, Issue 4, 2017.686 Basavaraj et al. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*
31. Associates in medical and cosmetic dermatology p.c, skin savvy, edition 2008.
32. www.pharaminfo.net.
33. Thornfeldt C. Cosmeceuticals containing herbs: fact, fiction, and future. *Dermatol Surg.* Jul 2005; 31: 873-80.
34. Padma PJ, Karthika: Cosmeceuticals-an evolution; *Int. J. Chem Tech Res.* 2009; 1(4): Dept. of Pharmaceutics, K.M.C.H College of pharmacy, Coimbatore-641 048 India.
35. Tasic Kostov M, Savic S, Lukic M, Tamburic S, Pavlovic M, Vuleta G. Lactobionic acid in a natural alkylpolyglucoside based vehicle: assessing safety and efficacy aspects in comparison to glycolic acid. *J cosmet dermatol.* Mar 2010; 9(1): 3-10.
36. Gollnick H, Cunliffe W, Berson D, et al. Management of acne. A report from a global alliance to improve outcomes in acne. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 2003; 46: S1-S38.
37. Leyden JJ. A review of the use of combination therapies for the treatment of acne vulgaris. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 2003; 49: S200-10.
38. Berson DS, Chalker DK, Harper JC, et al. Current concepts in the treatment of acne: report from a clinical roundtable. *Cutis* 2003; 72: 5-19.
39. Griffiths CEM. Nicotinamide 4% gel for the treatment of inflammatory acne vulgaris. *J Dermatol Treat* 1995; 6: S8-S10.
40. Bisset DL. Topical niacinamide and barrier enhancement. *Cutis* 2002; 70S: 8-12.
41. Bisset DL, Oblong JE, Berge CA. Niacinamide: a B vitamin that improves aging facial skin appearance. *Dermatol Surg* 2005; 31: 860-6.
42. Saurat JH. Skin, sun, and vitamin A: from aging to cancer. *J Dermatol* 2001; 28: 595-8.
43. Griffiths CEM, Russman AN, Majmudar G, et al. Restoration of collagen formation in photo damaged human skin by tretinoin (retinoic acid). *N Engl J Med* 1993; 329: 530-5.
44. Kang S, Voorhess JJ. Photo aging therapy with topical tretinoin: an evidence based analysis. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 1998; 39: S55-S61.
45. Creidi P, Vienne MP, Ochonisky S, et al. Profilometric evaluation of photo damage after retinaldehyde and retinoic acid treatment. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 1998; 39: 960-5.
46. Dahiya A, Romano JF. Cosmeceuticals: a review of their use for aging and photoaged skin. *Cosmet Dermatol* 2006; 19: 479-84.
47. Thiele JJ, Ekanayake Mudiyanse S, Hsieh SN. Cosmeceutical vitamins: vitamin E. In: Draelos ZD, editor. *Cosmeceuticals*. 1st Ed. Philadelphia (Pa): Elsevier Saunders; 2005. p. 47-54. Kosmadaki MG, Gilchrest BA. The role of telomeres in skin aging/ photo aging. *Micron* 2004; 35: 155-9. Basavaraj et al. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*
49. Thiele JJ, Ekanayake Mudiyanse S, Hsieh SN. Cosmeceuticals vitamins: vitamin E. In: Draelos ZD, editor. *Cosmeceuticals*. 1st ed. Philadelphia (Pa): Elsevier Saunders; 2005; 47-54.
50. Sorg O, Tran C, Saurat JH. Cutaneous vitamins A and E in the context of ultraviolet or chemically-induced oxidative stress. *Skin Pharmacol Appl Skin Physiol* 2001; 14: 363-72.
51. Lin JY, Selim MA, Shea CR, et al. UV photo protection by combination topical antioxidants vitamin C and vitamin E. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 2003; 48: 866-74.
52. Oblong JE, Bisset DL. Retinoids. In: Draelos ZD, editor. *Cosmeceuticals*. 1st ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier Saunders; 2005; 35-45.
53. Hakozaiki T, Minwalla L, Zhuang J, et al. The effect of niacinamide on reducing cutaneous

- pigmentation and suppression of melanosome transfer. *Br J Dermatol* 2002;147: 20-31.
54. Bisset DL, Oblong JE, Berge CA. Niacinamide: a B vitamin that improves aging facial skin appearance. *Dermatol Surg* 2005; 31: 860-6.
 55. Farris PK. Topical Vitamin C: a useful agent for treating photo aging and other dermatologic conditions. *Dermatol Surg* 2005; 31: 814-8.
 56. Pinnell SR, Yang HS, Omar M, et al. Topical L-ascorbic acid: percutaneous absorption studies. *Dermatol Surg* 2001; 27: 137-42.
 57. Perricone NV. The Photo protective and anti-inflammatory effect of Topical ascorbylpalmitate. *J Geriatr Dermatol* 1993; 1: 5-10.
 58. Pinnel SR. Cutaneous photo damage, oxidative stress and topical anti-oxidation protection. *J Am Acad Dermatol* 2003.